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On Some Criteria to Determine the Mongolian Borrowings in Kyrgyz

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The Turkic and Mongolic languages, regardless of the question of their genetic relationship, exhibit a substantial number of lexical, morphological, and syntactic correspondences, and research shows that a significant majority of similarities can be explained through the mutual influence (for more details see Schönig 2003: 403-419.).

Indeed, age-long, intense contacts between the speakers of the Turkic and Mongolian languages, the beginning of which is generally attributed to the time of the Huns (1st-6th centuries CE), have promoted the mutual penetration of lexical and grammatical (including morphological and syntactical) elements from each language group into the other. The pieces of evidence attested in a variety of historical and linguistic sources show that contacts and interactions between the speakers of these two language groups have been most intense and continuous in the Sayan-Altay and Tien-Shan regions.

Among the Turkic languages, the languages spoken in these contact zones, especially Tuvan, Yakut, and Kyrgyz have been strongly influenced by Mongolic languages. (Kazakh also can be mentioned next to Kyrgyz as the closest sister language in all respects, although Kazakh does not have Mongolian elements that are common to the South Siberian Turkic languages and Kyrgyz.)

The presence of an abundance of Mongolian elements in the Tuvan language is mainly due to the Tuvan-Mongolian asymmetric bilingualism in favor of the latter developed owing to socio-political and religious reasons and showed itself through later lexical copies mainly from Khalkha Mongolian (Tatarintsev 1976: 3-15; Khabtagaeva 2009: 21-25).

S. Kałuźiński studying the influence of Mongolian on Yakut, concluded that Mongolisms in Yakut either belong to an unknown Mongolian language or were copied at separate times from different Mongolic languages

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(Kałužiński 1962: 119-128). On the other hand, V.M. Nadelyaev argued that the Mongol layer of Yakut occurred due to the Khitans. He was of the idea that the Yakut people were formed on the Middle Lena based on the ethnic fusion of the ancient Turkic Kurykans with Khitans in the 11th – 12th centuries (Nadeljajev 1981: 15; Nadeljajev 1986: 14)

The third key language is Kyrgyz (Ščerbak (1986: 49). Rassadin (1987: 127-134) also noted that the largest number of Mongolian copies among the Kipchak languages were fixed in Kyrgyz and according to him these elements could penetrate this language only during the periods of long-term bilingualism within the same Turko-Mongolian *sprachbund*.

Kyrgyz is also unique in that it displays not only simple vocabulary transfers represented by lexical loans which in varying degrees can be seen in other Turkic languages as well, but also linguistic units that can be described as consequences of the influence of the Mongolian substrate, which is rarely the case for other Turkic languages.

It is well known that language reflects the lives of its speakers, so even a quick glance at the history of Kyrgyz can be enough to understand how their past is closely intertwined with the history of the Mongolian-speaking peoples. Here it would be enough to mention that the Kyrgyz were part of the early alliance of the “four Oirat” tribes (*Dorben Oirad*) and the final stages of the ethnogenesis of the Kyrgyz people took place during XIV-XVII centuries in the state of Mughalistan, which is also well-known as Eastern Chagatai Khanate, where Kyrgyz tribes united with the *Mughal* ones, who gradually undergone Turkicization through a linguistic shift and eventually formed with them a single ethnicity (Petrov 1961: 175-207; Petrov 1963: 130-145; Judin 1965: 68-69; Abramzon 1971: 58-64). At the same time, it should be mentioned that the Kyrgyz ethnicity included splinter tribes of the western, central, and northern Mongols, such as the *Alakč'in*, *Naiman*, *Merkit*, *Baarin*, *Kereit*, *Jalair*, *Qatakin*, *Dughlat* and a large separate group under the general name of *Monoldor* (*verbatim* the Mongols) which caused the appearance of heterogeneous lexical copies of Mongolic origin in Kyrgyz.

It should also be pointed out that in Kyrgyz, along with the explicit examples of both borrowing and substrate interference, there are many cases where it is also challenging to determine whether to attribute a specific linguistic phenomenon due to contact borrowing, or the influence of the substrate. The Turkic-Mongolian language contact lasted for centuries, during which contact occurred at continually varying levels of intensity. Linguistic dominance also shifted back and forth between Mongolic languages and Kyrgyz. In this way, substrate-related influences are intermingled with layers of borrowing. Therefore, it seems more reliable not to adopt a sharp distinction between interference via shift and borrowing, but rather to view the two on a continuum.

The question of the influence of Turkic-Mongolian language contacts on the formation of certain Turkic languages has already been discussed in relevant linguistic and historical studies. Along with the names of pioneers of this domain like G. J. Ramstedt, G. Nemeth, B. J. Vladimirtsov, N. Poppe, G. Clauson, G. Doerfer, A. M. Ščerbak, etc., it is noteworthy to mention the names of such linguists as S. Kałuziński (1962) for his works on Mongolian loan words (MLW) in Yakut, B. I. Tatarintsev (1976), M. Ölmez (2007), B. Khabtagaeva (2009), for MLW in Tuvan, V. Rassadin (1980) for MLW in South Siberian Turkic, B. Bazylhan (1967) and Š. Sarybaev (1971) for MLW in Kazakh, E. F. Išberdin (1979) and A. Vahitova (2010) for MLW in Bashkir, É. Csáki (2006) for MLW in Volga Kipchak languages, Sujunčev (1977) for MLW in Karachay-Balkar, Sydykov (1966) for MLW in Kyrgyz, É. Kincses-Nagy (2018) for MLW in Chaghatay, V. Rybatzki (2013, 2015, 2017) for MLW in Uzbek, C. Schönig (2000) for MLW in West Oghuz languages.

However, surprisingly, the topic of borrowings and/or Mongolian-based contact-induced changes in Kyrgyz has never been studied in detail, except for the works by Sydykov (1966, 1967, 1983), where the author follows the principle of the genealogical relationship of the Altaic languages and analyses the common vocabulary of the Kyrgyz and Mongolian languages not from the perspective of borrowings, but as common Turkic and Mongolian lexical parallels. What highlights these works is the fact that they were one of the first publications on the subject, however, it should be noted that they do not provide an answer to the fundamental question of what can be considered borrowings from the Mongol languages in Kyrgyz, and what are the criteria for identifying the borrowings of Mongolian origin in Kyrgyz.

The very first work that deals with the Mongolic borrowings in Kyrgyz was of A. Bulakaeva-Barannikova (1958: 113-143) followed by the works of S. Kudaibergenov (1964: 41-46; 1965: 39-49), K. Dyjkanov (1980: 71-77) where they discuss the question again from the perspective of the genetically common lexical parallels, which does not allow to clarify the key issues mentioned above. Recent studies on the subject are of G. Uzun (2011: 1835-1848; 2012: 305-310), S. Jumaliev (2000: 128-132), and K. Kalieva (2021: 21-42), however, they also did not give a clear answer to the above-mentioned question. Therefore, in this study, I will focus on the criteria used to determine Mongolic elements in Kyrgyz. I should note that it is beyond the scope of this article to determine the temporal stratification of Mongolian borrowings and the main source languages of such borrowings in the Kyrgyz language.

The identification of Mongolian copies in Turkic languages, in general, and in certain modern Turkic languages in particular has already been discussed and as a result, certain criteria have been developed in the works on Turkic-Mongolic language contact of authors such as G. Nemeth (1912: 549-

576; 1912: 401-412; 1914: 126-142), G. Clauson (1960: 301-316), N. Poppe (1969: 207-214), A. Rona-Tas (1974: 31-45), L. G. Gerzenberg (1974: 46-55), G. Doerfer (1963-1975) N. A. Syromjatnikov (1975: 50-61), N. D. Andreev & O. P. Sunik (1982: 26-29), A. M. Ščerbak (1996: 199-203), V. Rassadin (1988: 103-107; 2007; 208; 2014), É. Csáki (2006), B. Khaptagaeva (2009), É. Kincses-Nagy (2018) and others.

Many of these criteria are applicable when identifying Mongolian borrowings in Kyrgyz as well, but in Kyrgyz, too, there are such borrowings of Mongolian origin that can be found only in this language or in a particular group of Turkic languages. This suggests that the ancestors of Kyrgyz and Mongolian-speaking peoples had close contact in the past with the speakers of the given languages. Thus, among the criteria for identifying Mongolian borrowings in Kyrgyz the following can be mentioned.

I. The main criterion

The main criterion is the phonetic and semantic overlapping of a word in Kyrgyz (or in any of the Turkic languages) with the corresponding one in Mongolian, either earlier or later stage of its development, provided that this word is not recorded in Old Turkic, not seen, or seen rarely in other modern Turkic languages while is widespread in Mongolic languages.

e.g.: Kyrg. *čečekey* “eye lens” ← Mong., cf. LM. *čeče-gei* “apple of the eye”, HMog. *цецгий*, Kalm. *цецгэ*, Bur. *сэсэгы* “id.”; Kyrg. *čekit* “point, dot” < Mong., cf. LM. *čeg*, HMog., Kalm. *цэг*, Bur. *сэг* “point, dot; comma”, Kyrg. *kelen*, *kep kelen* “talk, conversation” ← Mong., cf. LM. *kele(n)* “tongue; anything resembling the tongue bell clapper, tongue of a buckle, etc.; language, dialect, speech”, HMog. *хэл(эн)*, Bur. *хэле(н)*, Ojr. *келен*, Kalm. *келн* “id.”. Kyrg. *ulut* “nation” ← Mong. (← OldT. *ulus*), cf. LM. *ulus*, HMog. *улс*, Bur. *улас*, *улад* “nation, people; state” (Old Mongolian coda *s became -d in Buriad), Ojr. *улас* (*улус*), Kalm. *улс* “id.” etc.

II. The etymological criterion

If the origin of a word has its explanation only based on Mongolian languages, then this word is considered etymologically Mongolian.

e.g.: Kyrg. *kelekey* “one who has a speech defect” ← Mong., cf. LM. *kelekey* (< *kele ügei*) “dumb, mute; stammering, stammering, tongue-tied”; HMog. *хэлгий*, Bur. *хэлегүй* “id.”, *келкэ* (*келкей*) “заика”, Kalm. *келкэ* “заика; заикающийся, косноязычный”. Kyrg. *megejin* “pig, sow” ← Mong. *mege-jin*, cf. LM. *megeji* “sow”; HMog. *мэгж*, Bur. *мэгэжэ* “дикая свинья (самка)”, Ojr. *мэгжи* (мегежи), Kalm. *мэгж* (мэгже) “id.”; Kyrg. *dörböljün-törböljün* ← Mong. *dörbeljin* (<*dörben* + *-ljin*) “square, rectangle; square felt cushion”, cf. LM. *dörbelji(n)* “square, rectangle; cube; square block; dice; diamonds (in cards); square felt cushion, square basket; square,

rectangular, cubic”, HMog. *дөрвөлж(ин)*, Bur. *дүрбэлжэн* “четырёхугольный, квадратный; четырёхугольник, квадрат”, Ojr. *дөрвөлжин (дөрбүлжин)*, Kalm. *дөрвлжн (дөрвелжен)* “id.” etc.

III. The semantic criterion

If a word has a wider meaning in Mongolic languages but has only a special or limited meaning in Kyrgyz (or in any Turkic language), it can be regarded as a Mongolian lexical loan.

e.g.: Kyrg. *сёсөн* “eloquent, silver-tongued” ← Mong., cf. LM. *сёсөн* ~ *сесэн* “wise, sage, intelligent, prudent”, HMog. *цэцэн*, Bur. *сэсэн*, Ojr. *цецен*, Kalm. *цэцн (цэчен)* “id.”; Kyrg. *jol* “good luck, fortune, good result, success” < Mong. (← OldT. *yol* (via *ǰol*) “road”), cf. LM. *jol* “good luck, fortune”, HMog., Bur., Ojr. *зол* “id.” etc.

Some words of Turkic origin during their adaptation to Mongolian may obtain a new meaning in them, which is preserved when borrowed back in Kyrgyz.

e.g.: Kyrg. *buluŋ* “corner (mainly its inner side); bay, gulf” ← Mong. (← OldT. *buluŋ* “corner, angle”), cf. LM. *bulung* corner, angle, end; bend of a river; bay, gulf”, HMog., Bur. *булан(г)* “id.”, Ojr. *булаң (булуң)* “угол”, Kalm. *булң (бульң)* “угол; уголок; излучина, кривизна, бухта”; Kyrg. *qurč* “steel; sharp; sword; frisky, hot; resolute, courageous; strength, power” ← Mong. (← probably PT. **qurčā*, cf. OldT. *qurč* “tough, hard”), cf. LM. *qurča* sharp, acute; quick, prompt, agile, nimble, alert, swift, adroit, keen; intelligent; bright; too oily, greasy, rich (of food), HMog. *хурц* “id.”, Bur. *хурса* “острый, наточенный”, Ojr. *хурца*, Kalm. *хурц (хурцъ)* “id.” etc.

IV. The criterion of synonyms

If there are two or more different words in Kyrgyz to denote the same thing and one of them is used also in Mongolic languages, then it is probably a loanword from Mongolian.

e.g.: Kyrg. *qol qap* “glove(s), mitten(s)” (← T., cf. Kaz., Uzb. *qol qap*, Tuv. *xol xap* (*verbatim* hand pouch) vs. *meeley* “id.” ← Mong. cf. LM. *begelei*, HMog. *бээлий*, Kalm *бээлэ*, Bur. *бээлей* “glove(s), mitten(s)”; Kyrg. *siŋga* “earring” (← OldT. *isirka*) vs. *söykö* “id.” ← Mong., cf. LM. *süyükü*, HMog. *сүйх*, Bur. *хиухе*, Ojr. *сиике (сиики)*, Kalm. *сиик (сиике)* “id.”; Kyrg. *ermen* “Artemisia, wormwood, sage” (← T., Kaz. *ермен*, Uzb. *erman*, Hak. (Kač., Koyb.) *erbän* (Radloff 1893: 800), Bašk. *эрем*, Tat. *эрём ути* “id.” (→ Mong. LM. *erm-e*, HMog. *эрэм* “Artemisia Sieversiana, Artemisia macrocephala”) vs. *širaljīn* “id.” ← Mong., LM. *siraljī(n)* “safe-brush, Artemisia vulgaris”, HMog. *šarilj*, Bur. *шаралза*, Ojr. *шаралжсин*, Kalm. *шарлжн* “id.” etc.

V. The criterion of cultural history

These are words that were formed in the cultural and political environment of the Mongolian peoples and the Mongolian medieval states.

Kyrg. *qarača* “common people, commoner” ← Mong. (← OldT. *qaračī* “beggar”), LM. *qaraču* “common people, commoner”, HMog. *харц*, Ojr. *харца* (*хараца*), Kalm. *харчуд* “id.”; Kyrg. *qaravul* “guard” ← Mong., cf. MM. *qara’ul* “guard”, LM. *qarağul* “watch, sentry, guard, scout”, HMog., Bur., Ojr. *харуул*, Kalm. *харул* “id.”; Kyrg. *nökör* “servant; comrade” ← Mong., cf. MM. *nökör*, *nöker* “friend, spouse”, LM. *nökür* “friend, comrade, companion; husband”, HMog. *нөхөр*, Bur. *нүкэр*, Ojr. *нөкер* (*нөкүр*), Kalm. *нөкр* “id.” etc.

VI. Phonetic criteria

a) Phonetic criteria for the words of Mongolic origin

1. *d-* doesn’t occur in initial position of originally Turkic words in Kyrgyz, except some words like *de-* “to say”. That is not the case for Mongolian.

e.g.: Kyrg. *daq* “stain, scar” ← Mong., cf. LM. *dag* “mark, sign, omen; speck of dust or dirt”, HMog., Bur., Ojr., Kalm. *дар* “id.”; Kyrg. *daban* ~ *dabaan* “mountain pass” ← Mog. cf. MM. *daban* “mountain pass”, LM. *dabağan* “mountain pass; mountain range; difficulty, obstacle victory in a contest”, HMog. *даваа*, Bur. *дабаа(н)*, Oyr. *даваан* (*дабаан*), Kalm. *давлһн* (*давльһһн*) “id.”, Kyrg. *daa-* “to dare, venture” ← Mog., cf. LM. *dağağa-*, *dağa-* “to be able to carry, bear, or lift”, HMog., Bur., Ojr., Kalm. *daa-* “id.” etc.

2. *-VdV-*: *-d-* doesn’t occur in intervocalic position in the words of Turkic origin in Kyrgyz (if it has not become voiced secondarily from an earlier *-t-*).

e.g.: Kyrg. *badıray-* “to flame, blaze; (about eyes) to be big and beautiful” ← Mong., cf. LM. *badara-* “to spread, expand, develop; to flame, blaze, flare; to be(come) inspired, be carried away; to become clear, manifest, public; to clear up”, HMog. *батра-*, *бадар-*, Bur., Ojr. *бадара-*, Kalm. *бадра-* (*бадрaa-*) “id.”; Kyrg. *qada* “to stick” ← Mong., cf. LM. *qada-* “to drive in, to knock in; to nail; to inscribe or enter one’s name on a register; to register something in a text, to get stuck”, HMog., Kalm. *хад-*, Bur., Ojr. *хадa-* “id.” etc.

3. *-VjV-*: *-j-* doesn’t occur in intervocalic position in original Turkic words in Kyrgyz, except the lexical copies of Russian, Arabo-Persian and Mongolian origin.

e.g.: Kyrg. *aǰa* “elder” ← Mong. (← T., cf. OldT. *eči* “elder, uncle”), cf. HMOg. *ажаа* “father; aunt” (BAMRS 190a); Bur. *ажаа* “mother, honorific address to the father's mother”; Kyrg. *кејим* “gold-woven fabric; saddle cloth, blanket” ← Mong. (← OldT. *kedim* “clothes”, cf. LM. *kejim* “caparison, saddle cloth”, HMOg. *хэжим*, Bur. *хэжэм*, Kalm. *кежэм* “id.”; Kyrg. *qajǰa*- to nimble, gnaw; chafe” ← Mong., cf. LM. *qajǰa*- “to bite, gnaw, nibble”, HMOg. *хаза*-, Ojr. Kalm., Bur. *хаз*- “id.” etc.

4. *m*- (if it has not developed secondarily from a *b*-). This consonant doesn't occur in initial position of the words of the Turkic origin, except some onomatopoeic words.

e.g.: Kyrg. *maqta*- “to praise, to glorify” ← Mong., cf. LM. *maǰta*- “to praise, eulogize, laud, extol, glorify”, HMOg., Bur., Ojr. *магта*-, Kalm. *макт*- “id.” etc.; Kyrg. *maqoo* “stupid, foolish, dump” ← Mong., cf. LM. *maqqu* “stupid (person), lout, clod”, HMOg. *мангуу*, *манхуу*, Bur. *мунхаг*, Ojr. *муңхаг*, Kalm. *муңхг* (*муңхгьг*) “неразумный, невежественный, отсталый, глупый”; Kyrg. *möndür* “hail” ← Mong., cf. LM. *möndür* “hail, sleet”, HMOg. *мөндөр*, Bur. *мүндэр*, Ojr. *мөндер* (*мөндөр*), Kalm. *мөндр* “id.” etc.

5. *n*-, similarly to the previous consonants it cannot stand in initial position in Turkic languages.

e.g.: Kyrg. *narin* “a meal of finely chopped meat and noodles” ← Mong. cf. LM. *narin* “fine (not coarse); narrow, tight; thin, slender; high-pitched”, HMOg. *нарийн*, Bur. *нарин*, Ojr. *нэрен* (*нарин*), Kalm. *нэрн* “тонкий, узкий”; Kyrg. *niqī*- “press firmly” ← Mong., cf. LM. *niqu*-, *niqu*- “to rub, massage; to mash, press, knead; to crumple; to finish off, dispose of completely, kill”, HMOg., Kalm. *нух*-, Bur. *нюха*-, Ojr. *нуха*- “мять, разминать, размягчать; расмешивать, растирать; месить; протирать; тереть (глаза)”; Kyrg. *нура*-, *ура*- (< *нура*-) “to fall, collapse” ← Mong. cf. LM. *nura*- “to crumble, fall, collapse”, HMOg., Kalm. *нур*-, Bur., Ojr. *нура*- “id.” etc.

6. *š*-, similarly to the previous consonants it cannot stand in initial position in Turkic languages.

e.g.: Kyrg. *šaǰši*- “to chirp, tweeter, chirrup” ← Mong., cf. LM. *šaǰši*-, *šaǰsira*- to chatter (of magpies); to click the tongue (in praise or admiration)”, HMOg. *шагши*- “id.”, Ojr. *шагши*- “идти гурьбой, лететь стаей; стрекотать (о сороках)”, Kalm. *шагш*- (*шагшь*-) “идти гурьбой”; Kyrg. *širdaq* “felt carpet; saddlepath” ← Mong., cf. LM. *sirdeg* “matress; saddlepath”, HMOg. *ширдэг*, Bur. *шэрдэг*, Ojr. *ширдег* (*ширидег*), Kalm. *ширдг* “id.”; Kyrg. *šilen*, *šilee* “bullion” ← Mong., cf. LM. *silen* “soup, buillon, broth”, HMOg. *шөл(өн)*, Bur. *шүлэн*, Ojr. *шөлен* (*шөлөн*), Kalm. *шөлн* “id.” etc.

b) Phonetic criteria for Mongolic words of Turkic origin

1. The stem-final vowels.

The stem-final vowels were gradually reduced and disappeared until Old Turkic, with few remnants and traces in it, however, they were preserved in Turkic copies in Mongolic languages and are reflected in the back-borrowings in Kyrgyz.

e.g.: Kyrg. *quča* “(male) lamb” ← Mong. (← Turkic, probably from PT. **qōčā* >> Kyrg. *qočqor*), cf. MM. *quča* “lamb”, LM. *quča* “ram; uncastrated lamb”, HMog. *xyu*, Bur. *xyca*, Kalm. *xyca* “id.”; Kyrg. *qira* “edge, rim; border mountain hollow; ridge, edge of a mountain” ← Mong. (← Turkic, probably PT. **qirā*, cf. OldT. *qir* “an isolated mountain or block of mountains; edge” >> Kyrg. *qir*, *qiraŋ* “id.”), cf. LM. *kira* “summit or ridge of a mountain; small mountain chain; foothills; slope; a trip (usually of horn) attached to the front and rear edges of the saddle”, HMog. *хяр*, Bur. *хяра*, Ojr. *киле* (*кили*) “border, verge, frontier”, Kalm. *кир* “size, measure”; Kyrg. *sura* “to ask (a question); to inquire (about smth)” ← Mong. (← Turkic, probably from PT. **sōrā* “id.”), cf. MM. *sori-*, *sora-* “id.”, LM. *sura* “to learn, to be accustomed; to ask, inquire”, HMog., Kalm. *сур-*, Bur. *хура-*, Ojr. *супа-* “id.” etc.

2. Turkic-Mongolian rhotasism

It is assumed that Proto-Bulgharic or Oguric **r*₂ (or **r*′) preserved the Pre-Turkic state of affairs and this has been reflexed in early Mongolic loans from Proto-Bulgharic Turkic, whereas in Common Turkic it has evolved into *z*. Cognates in Kyrgyz where one of the pairs is a back-borrowing clearly show this development.

e.g.: Kyrg. *aŋiraqay* ← Mong. (← Turkic, probably PT. **ağir*, cf. OldT. *ağiz* “mouth (in an anatomic sense; the mouth (of a river) or any sort of aperture”, DLT *ağ* “the space between the legs, crotch”), cf. LM. *anggarqai* “crevice, cranny, fissure; gaping, having a gap; slightly open, ajar (as a door), HMog., Bur. *ангархай* “id.”, also LM. *ağurqai* “mine, shaft; hole, pit; source, beginning; secret or hidden place”, HMog. *уурхай* “id.”; Kyrg. *araan* “no definite meaning, a mouth-related word”, e.g., *araanı ačiq* “insatiable, greedy”) ← Mong. (← Turkic, probably PT. **ariğā*, cf. OldT. *azığ* “id.”), cf. MM. *ari’a*, LM. *arağa* (<**ariğa*) “molar; canine tooth; tusk”, HMog. *апаа*, Bur., Ojr. *араан*, Kalm. *аран* “id.”; Kyrg. *qimīran* “boiled milk with water” ← Mong. (← Turkic, probably PT. **qimīr*, cf. OldT. *qimīz* “fermented mare’s milk, koumiss”), Mong. cf. LM *qimurağan*, Kalm. *kimr* “kumys mit wasser (als trunk), “*kimrān* “gekochte kuhmilch mit wasser gemischt” (Ramstedt 1935: 281), Ojr. *кимер* (*кимир*) “кипяченая вода с молоком” etc.

3. Turkic-Mongolian lambdaism

As in the case of Turkic-Mongolian rhotacism, Proto-Turkic **l₂* evolved into Common Turkic *š* while in Proto-Bulgharic it has preserved itself. There are loans of Turkic origin in Kyrgyz that reflect this situation

e.g.: Kyrg. *dalda* “shelter,; nook; shady spot” ← Mong. (← Turkic, probably PT. **dal-*, cf. OldT. *yaš-* “to hide, conceal”, Kyrg. *jašir-* “id.”), cf. LM *dalda* “hidden, concealed, secret(ly); latent(ly); reticent(ly); illegal(ly); secret, something hidden or unknown”, HMog., Kalm. *далд*, Bur. *далда* “тайно, скрытно”, Ojr. *далда* “скрытный, тайный, секретный”; Kyrg. *alči* “the vertical side of the anklebone with an ear-like depression (in *astragalus* game)” ← Mong. (← Turkic, probably PT. **elček*, cf. OldT. *ešek, eškeк, ešyек* “id.”), cf. LM. *eljige(n)* “donkey”, HMog. *илжиг*, илжгэн, Bur. *элжэгэ(н)*, Ojr. *элжиген*, Kalm. *элжгн (элжген)* “id.”; Kyrg. *sal, zalun* “youth, a young man”, *jaloon* “agile, alert, dexterous” ← Mong. **jalagun* (< *jal-A+gUn*) ← Turkic, probably PT. **jal*, cf. OldT. *yaš* “fresh, moist” >> Kyrg. *jaš* “young, youthful; youth; fresh, moist”, cf. MM. *jalaḡu, jala’u, jalau*, LM. *jalaḡu* “young, youthful; youth; youthfulness”, HMog., Bur., Kalm. *залуу* “id.”, Ojr. *залуу* “мужчина; муж, супруг; юный, молодой” etc.

4. PT. *ḍ*- > Mong. *d*- >> Kyrg. *d*-.

Proto-Turkic voiced dental spirant *ḍ* (or *d₂*) in the initial position which yielded *y*- in Old Turkic becomes plosive *d*- in Mongolian (see Clauson 1959: 186).

e.g.: Kyrg. *daaqi* “spring wool (not yet faded); fig. rags, shreds” ← Mong. (← Turkic *ḍabaqu*, cf. OldT. *yapaqu* “colt, flees wool” >> Kyrg. *jabaḡi* “molting; spring sheep wool”), cf. LM. *daḡaki* “snarl, tangle; combings of hair; shedding of hair; hair of child before cutting it for the first time”, HMog. *даахь*, Bur. *даахи* “id.”, Ojr. *дээке (дааки)*, Kalm. *дээк (дээке)* “свалявшийся, спутавшийся (о волосах, шерсти)”; Kyrg. *dayin* “enemy, hostile” ← Mong. (← Turkic **daḡi*, cf. OldT. *yaḡi* “enemy, hostile; war” >> Kyrg. *joо* “id.”), cf. LM. *dain* “war, battle; hostility, enmity”, HMog., Bur. *дайн*, Ojr. *дээн (дайн)*, Kalm. *дэн* “война” etc.

5. OldT. *-ḍ*- > Mong. *-d*- >> Kyrg. *-d*-.

Old Turkic intervocal *-ḍ-* is preserved as plosive *d* in Mongolic, while in Turkic it developed into *-y-*.

e.g.: Kyrg. *quduq* “draw-well” ← Mong. (← OldT. *quduḡ* “id.” >> Kyrg. *quy(u)* “hole, pit”), cf. LM. *quduḡ, qudduḡ* “well”, HMog., Bur. *худаг*, Ojr. *худаг (худуг)*, Kalm. *худг* “id.”; Kyrg. *siḍir-* “to scrape off, rip off; to ride or walk carefully inspecting sb. or smth.” ← Mong. (← OldT. *siḍir-* “to strip, peel, scrape and the like” >> Kyrg. *siyir-* “id.”), LM. *sidur-* “to rise,

stand, erect, straighten; to pull the reins by stretching the head forward or downward (of a horse)", НМог. *шудра*- "обрывать, отрывать, облуплять, царапать, соскабливать, скрести; зажигать спички"-, Вур. *шудар*- "скрести, соскребать; бороздить; чиркать (спичкой)", Оjr. *шудар*- (*шудур*-) "скрести, соскребать, соскабливать; задевать, касаться, бороздить" Kalm. *шудр* "id."; Кырг. *жайдақ* "without a saddle; unsaddled" ← Mong. (← OldT. *yabīdaq* "(of a horse) bare-backed, not saddled" via *jabīdaq* >> Alt. *дыабыдак*, Нак. *чабыдак* "id" etc.), cf. LM. *jaidang* "without a saddle; unsaddled", НМог. *зайдан*, Вур. *зайдан*, Оjr. *зээден* (*зайдан*), Kalm. *зээдн* "id." etc.

6. OldT. *sI* > Mong. *sI* > *šI* >> Кырг. *šI*.

Turkic does not allow *š* in the initial position, whereas in Mongol *š* developed from *si*- (> *ši*-). Therefore, the words in Kyrgyz with the initial *š*- that have cognates in other Turkic languages with the initial *s*-, are considered back-borrowings.

e.g.: Кырг. *šumqar* "falcon" ← Mong. **siŋqor* (← OldT. *suŋgur* "id.", cf. ТТ. *suŋgur* "id.") cf. LM. *šongqur*, *siŋqur* "falcon, gerfalcon", НМог. *шонхор*, Вур. *шонхор* "сокол, кречет", Оjr. *шоңхор*, Kalm. *шоңхр* "id."; Кырг. *tepsi* "washtub" ← Mong. (← OldT. *tepsi*, *tepsi* (← Chin. 碟子 *die zi* "bowl, plate"), cf. ТТ. *tepsi* "tray"), cf. ММ. *tebsin*, LM. *tepsi*, НМог., Kalm. *тэвш*, Вур. *тэвшэ* "небольшое корыто; деревянное блюдо", Оjr. *тевши* (тебши) "деревянное блюдо; корыто"; Кырг. *šiba*- "to smear, plaster" ← Mong. (← Turkic, probably **si:ba*-, cf. OldT. *suva*- "to plaster", ТТ. *siva*- "id.", Кырг. *сийпа*- "put or spread (something) on a surface"), cf. ММ. *suba*-, *šiba*- "id.", LM. *siba*- "to plaster, stucco; to apply mud; to apply ointment; to cover or gather thickly on something (as insects)", НМог. *шав*-, Вур. *шаба*-, Kalm. *шаврт*- (*шавьртъ*-) "id." etc.

7. OldT. *-š* > Mong. *-s*.

Mongolian does not have unvoiced plosives and affricates in the final position, therefore Turkic final *-š* alters to *-s*. Thus, those Mongolian loans in Kyrgyz that have cognates in Turkic with the final *-š* are considered back-borrowings.

e.g.: Кырг. *tos*- "to receive; to encounter, to block one's way, meet someone who is coming; to catch something moving toward the subject" ← Mong. (← OldT. *tuš*- "to encounter, meet"), cf. LM. *tos*- "to receive; to encounter, to meet someone who is coming; to catch something moving toward the subject" НМог. Оjr., Kalm. *мос*- "встречать, поджидать"; Кырг. *tegiš* ~ *tegis* "even, level, straight" ← Mong., cf. LM. *tegsi* (← probably OldT. *teng*+*sig* "equal; being the same in quantity, size, degree, or value"), НМог. *тэгш*, Вур. *тэгшэ*, Оjr. *тегши* "ровный, гладкий; ровно, поровну", Kalm.

mezui (mezue) “id.” Moreover Mong. *tegsi* → Kyrg. *tekši* “equally; entirely, uniformly”; Kyrg. *ulut* “nation; people” ← Mong. via Buryat type historical Mongolic dialect ← OldT. *uluš* “people, nation”), cf. LM. *ulus* “people, nation; country, state; empire, dynasty”, HMog. *uls*, Bur. *ulad*, *ulas* “people, population, nation” Jalait-Durbet dialect in Inner Mongolia *ult* “id.” (Todayeva 1981: 214) etc.

8. OldT. *tI-* > Mong. *či-*

It is well known that *t* and *d* in Mongolian does not occur before *i* (or **i*) and in this position, it became *č* and *ǰ* respectively. Turkic copies that contain *tI-* and *dI-* underwent this phonetic change during their adaptation. This sound shift *dI-/ti-* > *ji-/či-* appears in Mongolian before 11th century but was still ongoing even during the 13th-century (see Sanjeev 1953: 94; Schönig 2005: 150). Kyrgyz has Mongolian borrowings that reflect these regular shifts.

e.g.: Kyrg. *čïyraq* “strong, hardy; dexterous” ← Mong. (← OldT. *tïgraq* “strong, hardy” (<*tïgra-q*)), cf. MM. *çi'irax* “strong, hardy”, LM. *čigirağ* “strong, robust, powerful; massive, solid; vigorous”, HMog. *чуйрэг*, Bur. *шууга* “сильный, здоровый, крепкий”, Ojr. *чуурег*, Kalm. *чуург (чуурез)* “выносливый, сильный, крепкий”; Kyrg. *kayčï* “scissors” ← Mong. (← **qağiti* < **qabitï* < OldT. **qapitï*, cf. KBalk. *qiptï*, Hak. *qipta Yak. qiptïy* “id.”), cf. MM. *qaiči* “id.”, LM. *qaiči(n)* “scissors, tongs, pincers”, HMog. *хайч*, Bur. *хайша*, Ojr. *хээчи (хаичу)*, Kalm. *хээч* “ножницы”; Kyrg. *qačïr* “mule” etc. ← Mong. (← OldT. *qatïr* “mule”), cf. MM. **qačïr* “id.” Etc.

9. OldT. *dI-* > Mong. *ǰi-*

As in the case with *t* before *i* (or **i*), Mongolian does not allow *d* before *i* (or **i*) and when this is the case it became *ǰi* as a rule.

e.g.: Kyrg. *qajïr* “stubborn; determined, courageous; hardened (of a person)” ← Mong. (← OldT. *qadïr* “grim, brutal, oppressive, dangerous”, cf. Hak. *хазыр* “despot, tyrant; angry, wrathful, fierce, cruel”, Tuv. *кадыр* “steep, sheer”), cf. MM. *qajïr* “mighty, powerful”, LM. *qajïr* “id.”, Bur. *хажар* “придирчивый, вредный, злой”; Kyrg. *kejïge* “nape, back of the head” ← Mong. (← Pre-OldT. **keđi*, cf. OldT. *keđin* “behind (usually of place, less often of time; afterwards” >> Kyrg. *kiyin* “afterwards”), cf. LM. *gejïge* “nape of the neck, plait or braid of hari, pigtail, queue; hair in general”, *gede* “nape or back of the neck, occiput” + GAn (a denominal noun suffix), HMog. *зэзэз*, Bur. *зэзэз*, Kalm. *гижгэ* “коса, косички”; Kalm., Bur. (west dialect) “затылок”; HMog. “гребень на теневой стороне горы”; Kyrg. *müljü-* “to gnaw” ← Mong. (← ?OldT. **bulda-* >> Kyrg. *bulta-* “to jerk, to pull sharply”), cf. LM. *mölji-*, HMog., Kalm. *мөлж-*, -Bur. *мүлже-*, Ojr. *мөлжү-* “глодать, обгладывать” etc.

10. OldT. *č-* > Mong. *š-*.

e.g.: Kyrg. *šalbaa* “meadow; damp place with dense tall grass” ← Mong. (← OldT. *čalpak* “mud, sludge”), cf. LM. *šalbağ-a*, *šalbağ*, *šalbağag* “pool, puddle; mud”, HMog. *шалбааг шалбаа*, Bur. *шалбааг*, Kalm. *шалва* “id.”; Kyrg. *šiqa-* “to squeeze, stuff tightly, push” ← Mong. (← OldT. *sīq-* “id.”), cf. MM. *šiqa-* “id.”, LM. *siqa-*, *siğa-* “to press, squeeze, squash; to strain (by squeezing); to crowd; to oppress; to urge, force something upon somebody; to fatten for slaughter”, HMog., Bur., Ojr. *шаха-*, Kalm. *шах-* (*шахъ-*) “id.” etc.

11. Irregularities of OldT. *ağ* >> Kyrg. *oo*

The common reflex of the Old Turkic *-ağ* in Kyrgyz is *-oo* (e.g. OldT. *tag* “mountain” >> Kyrg. *too* “id.”, OldT. *sag* “alive, healthy” >> Kyrg. *soo* “id.” etc.), but some words of Turkic origin in Kyrgyz do not reflect this phonetic development. I tend to consider them as back-borrowings from Mongolian or words that were formed and spread in the Mongolian language environment.

e.g.: Kyrg. *saa-* “to milk” ← Mong. *saga-* (← probably PT. *sagā-*, cf. OldT. *sag-* “id.”), MM. *sa'a-*, *saga-*, LM. *saga-*, HMog., Ojr., Kalm. *caa-*, Bur. *haa-* “id.” Kyrg. *jaa-* “to rain; to snow” ←? Mong. **jağa-*; Kyrg. Kyrg. *ayil* “village, settlement, group of tents” ← Mong. *ayil* (← OldT. *ağil* “an enclosure for livestock; cattle-pen; sheep-fold; settlement or group of tents” >> Kyrg. *ağil* “cattle-pen; sheep-fold”) MM. *ayil*, LM. *ail* “family, household; homestead; neighbor(hood), settlement, group of tents, village”, HMog., Bur. *айл*, Ojr. *әәл* (*айл*), Kalm. *әәл* “id.”; Kyrg. *bayla-* ← Mong. **baila-* (← OldT. *bağ+la-* “to tie in bunches, to pack, wrap” >> Kyrg. *boo+lo-* “id.”) etc.

ABBREVIATIONS AND THE SOURCES FOR LEXICAL DATA

Alt.	Altai	see Čumakaev 2018
Bur.	Buryat	see Čeremisov 1951
Chin.	Chinese	
Hak.	Hakas	see Baskakov 1953
HMog.	Khalkha Mongolian	see Luvsandendev 2001
Kalm.	Kalmuck	see Muniev 1977
Kaz.	Kazakh	see Bektaev 1995
KBalk.	Karachay-Balkar	see
Kyrg.	Kyrgyz	see Judahin 1965
LM.	Literary Mongolian	see Lessing 1960
MM.	Middle Mongolian	see Nugteren 2011
Mong.	Mongolian	
Ojr.	Ojrat	see Todaeva 2001

OldT.	Old Turkic	see Clauson 1972
PT.	Proto-Turkic	
Tuv.	Tuvan	see Tenišev 1968
Uzb	Uzbek	see Kary-Nijazov 1941

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